

CLEANDEM

Cyber physical Equipment for unManned Nuclear DEcommissioning Measurements

CLEANDEM will deliver an **Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV) Platform equipped with upgraded radiological sensing probes to support dismantling and decommissioning (D&D) operations** – from the initial radiological assessment to the final characterization of the facility.

In this manner, CLEANDEM contributes to making D&D operations:

- **SAFER**, by minimizing human intervention and radiation exposure.
- **CLEANER**, by lowering environmental risks.
- **BETTER**, by improving measurements' quality through use of multiple online probes.
- **FASTER**, through autonomous acquisition of measurements by the robot.
- **CHEAPER**, through the adoption of low-cost, modular technologies.

RESULTS

UGV platform with upgraded radiological sensors

Other sensors

Follow the LinkedIn page **CLEANDEM Project**

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